

The effects of serotonin on regeneration of the planarian *Paucumara falcata*

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Abstract. Planarians, for their efficient regeneration capacity and establishment of a central nervous system, are suitable models for understanding stem cells potency and developmental neuroscience. The ubiquitous neurotransmitter, serotonin, was stated to have a vital role in the regeneration process. This research investigated the regenerative sexual reproduction effect of exogenous serotonin in a recently found marine planarian, *Paucumara falcata*. Contrary to freshwater species, this marine planarian showed dose-dependent retarded regeneration in presence of serotonin, suggesting possible variation in the species' serotonergic pathways; serotonin was shown to stimulate the production of cocoons in planarian.

1. Introduction

Planarians are the simplest group of animals that possess bilateral instead of radial symmetry, and cephalization [1]. Researchers also detected several classical neurotransmitters and receptors widely used by mammals such as acetylcholine, glutamate, and serotonin [2]. Ubiquitous in animal kingdom, serotonin can be synthesized in planarians through the conversion of tryptophan to 5-hydroxytryptophan, catalyzed by enzyme tryptophan hydroxylase, which gene was first identified in 2007 [3]. Many subtypes of serotonin receptors have also been reported to be present in planarians [4].

Planarians' regeneration capacity of quickly restoring damaged body parts and even brain makes it a suitable research model in developmental neuroscience [5] and research of stem cells potency. Studies found that serotonin plays a vital role in head regeneration [6] and eye regeneration [7], by speeding up both processes. This study aims to investigate how exogenous serotonin affects regenerative ability in a recently described marine planarian, *Paucumara falcata*.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Planarian culture

Sexually matured individuals of *P. falcata* were selected and maintained in 20 ppt brackish water. For the experiment, worms were transversely dissected with razor between the eye and the pharynx, each pair of head and tail were placed into 1 mL serotonin solution. At each concentration, 36 pairs of heads and tails were used, divided into three 12-pair subgroups.

The progress of regeneration was then observed twice a day for 7 days under the stereomicroscope. The regeneration of tail was considered to be completed when a pair of eyes was present; as for head, the presence of pharynx was considered as completion of regeneration process.

2.2 Compound

The stock solution of serotonin was 50 mmol dm⁻³, and it was serially diluted to 1.25 and 0.625 mmol dm⁻³ with 20 ppt brackish water prior to the experiment.

3. Results

3.1 Regeneration

Both head and tail regenerations were inhibited by application of serotonin solution, and the effect was in dose-dependent manner. As demonstrated in Figure 1, tailless individuals completed regeneration more quickly in the control group, and an average of 11.67 out of 12 heads have regenerated their tails on day 6. Both 0.625 and 1.25 mmol dm^{-3} groups had their first complete regeneration at day 4.5, one day later than in the control group (at day 3.5). The rate of successful regeneration was lower in the presence of serotonin. By the end of experiment only 58.3% had fully regenerated tails in 0.625 mmol dm^{-3} serotonin, 30.6% in 1.25 mmol dm^{-3} . In the case of heads, 63.9% have successfully regenerated heads by day 7 in the control group, 4.8% in 0.625 mmol dm^{-3} serotonin, and none in 1.25 mmol dm^{-3} serotonin.

Figure 1: The percentage of numbers of complete head (A) and tail (B) regeneration in different groups (0, 0.625, 1.25 mmol dm^{-3} serotonin).

In the case of incomplete regeneration, there were either little blastema regenerated, or abnormal developments of blastema (Fig.2). Most abnormalities occur in the experimental groups, indicating the normal regeneration process being disturbed.

Figure 2: Different types of abnormal regeneration. A) - H) heads regenerating abnormal or no tails. G) a head regenerating another head (a new pair of eyes present in the supposed tail part), I) tail regenerating a head part without eyes. All worms shown were from groups with serotonin.

3.2 Sexual reproduction

Apart from regeneration, a significant portion of headless individuals laid cocoons. As shown in Fig.3, 11.4% of individuals in control group laid one cocoon (combining the grey and orange sections) throughout the experiment. Interestingly, 57.1% and 44.1% of individuals laid one cocoon in $0.625 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$ and $1.25 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$ serotonin treatment group respectively. Overall, the experimental groups have a higher proportion of egg-laying tails than the control group.

Figure 3: Cocoon production and regeneration ratio in groups treated with different concentration of serotonin.

4. Discussion

Serotonin was reported to have stimulatory effects in head regeneration of planarian *Polycelis tenuis* [8], *Schmidtea mediterranea* and *Girardia tigrina* [9], research also highlighted its role in reformation of eyes [7]. However, the results of this experiment contradict this statement, as both head and tail regeneration were retarded with serotonin. This incongruence may be caused by the concentrations applied were too high for long-term exposure. Previous research used 0.5 [8] and 0.1 - 0.7 mmol dm⁻³ [10]. The conflicting result could also be due to the difference in species investigated. *P. falcata* belongs to the Maricola infraorder, which is different from all the species mentioned above [11]. Thus, this study may reflect unexpected variation in the species' serotonergic system. The abnormal regeneration observed also indicates that the exogenous application of serotonin can interfere the general regeneration process, but the exact impact, and whether it is dose-independent, requires further investigation with larger sample size under more sets of concentrations.

It could be proposed that serotonin stimulates the sexual reproduction in *P. falcata*, since more tails laid eggs when exogenous serotonin was applied. This result is consistent with current findings: serotonin was found to enhance the formation of ovaries in *Schmidtea mediterranea* [12]. However, the two concentrations investigated are insufficient to determine the dose-dependency of serotonin on sexual reproduction. The factors that impact sexual reproduction, such as time of mating and energy consumption for metabolic and regenerating processes, contribute to the inaccuracy of the results.

Serotonin is one of the most widespread neurotransmitters in the animal kingdom. Its ability to regulate tissue regeneration is found in mammals (liver regeneration), and in planarians (tissue regeneration). However, whether its effect is unified in all planarian species requires further verification. The observed inhibitory response in tissue regeneration of *P. falcata* suggests the need to outline the molecular mechanism for serotonin's action. Derivatives of serotonin, for example melatonin, should also be investigated to provide further evidence of the exact role of serotonin in planarians. Serotonin in planarians offers insights for the process of tissue regeneration, and considering planarian's neurological resemblance in mammals, this aids future research into regulating regeneration of neurosystems and tissues in mammals.

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